

Effects of Social Network among College Students

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Abstract

This paper is focused to discover the effect of social network services to college students. Now a day's Social Network Services provides various services like employment, marketing, personal growth, sharing of information etc., These Social Network Services has great impact on college students. These social networking services provide to communicate ideas to others, but it creates platform for many cyber crimes. So we focused on the fact that how Social Network Services are implementing and used in an effective manner that is also beneficial for college students. In this paper we are paying attention on the positive as well as negative impact of these social networking sites on the college students. Results indicate while most college students use social network services and spend many hours checking social network services, there was a positive aspect to college students' use of social network services.

Keywords: Social Network Services, Students Academic Performance.

Introduction

On the internet, people engage a variety of activities and get many services. In modern world, the technology and extraordinary development and changed the life cycle of many people. An exponential rise in usage of internet has been large sized in recent years. The website provides more information and services like Online shopping, E-Banking, E-Commerce and Social Networks etc.

Concept of Social Network

The social network is a major technological development changing student's social interaction. Social network sites involves the use of the internet to connect users with their friends families, unknown persons etc. The most well known social media sites are whatsapp, facebook, twitter, orkut, instagram and youtube etc. These sites allow to share photos, videos, information, organize events, chatting and play online games etc.

A social networking service is a platform to build social networks or social relations among students who share similar interests, activities, backgrounds or real life connections. A social network service consists of a representation of each user, his or her social

links and a variety of additional services such as career services. Social network sites are web-based services that allow individuals to create a public profile, create a public profile, and create a list of users with whom to share connections within the system.

According to the Oxford Dictionary, a “Social Network” is a dedicated website or other application that enables users to communicate with each other by posting information, comments, messages, images and etc., the main type of social networking services are those that contain category places (such as former school or classmates), means to connect with friends (usually with self description pages) and a recommendation system linked to trust.

Statement of the Problem

In recent trend educational institutions are engaging in social network can allow for highly participate interaction with students. Social media network have become more popular among students to make connections for various students. The emergence of social media had created opportunities to establish peer – support networks among the students. Social media networks changed the way of students interact with each others.

Now a days most of the students are spending time social networking sites. The students are always engaged using their mobiles, desktop computer, laptop, and tables etc., for text messaging, content sharing, online learning, chating and checking their facebook profiles. This is happen about 5 to 6 hours in daily and some time to full night. From this it is clear the students using social networks regularly.

This study investigates the effects of social network among college students.

Objectives of the Study

- To know the purpose of using social network among college students.
- To know the effects of social network among college students.

Methodology

The mechanism used for data collection for this study was the questionnaire method. The research study was based on a convenience sample. There were 50 students from an arts and science college who actively participated in this study.

Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1 Classification of Gender

S.No	Gender	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Male	28	56
2	Female	22	44
	Total	50	

From the above table shows that 56% respondents are male and 44% respondents are female.

Table 2 Classification of Major

S.No	Major	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Commerce	16	32
2	Science	14	28
3	Arts	10	20
4	Management	10	20
	Total	50	

From the table 2 refer 32% of students studied commerce, 28% of students studied science, 20% of students studied arts and management.

Table 3 No. of Members in Social Networking Services

S.No	Members in Social Network Services	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Less than 2	20	40
2	3 to 4	16	32
3	5 to 6	8	16
4	Above 7	6	12
	Total	50	

From the above table reveals that 40% of students members in less than 2 social network services, 32% of students members in 3 to 4 social network services, 16% of students members in 5 to 6 social network services and 12% of students members in above 7 social network services.

Table 4 Uses of Social Networking Services by Students

S. No	Time	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Less than 6 Months	11	22
2	6 Months to 1 Year	8	16
3	1 Year to 2 Years	10	20
4	Above 2 Years	21	42
	Total	50	

To find that how long students have been using Social Network Services. In the above table shows that only 22% students were using Social Network Services since last 6 months. 16% students are using it since 6 months to 1 year. 20% students were using since 1 year to 2 years and 42% were using it since more 2 years. Chart -2 below further displays the graphical distribution of the members in a social network sites.

Table 5 Social Networking Services Most used by Students

S. No	Social Networking Services	No. of Users	Percentage
1	Facebook	6	12
2	Whatsapp	30	60
3	Twitter	4	8
4	Youtube	3	6
5	Instagram	5	10
6	Others	2	4
	Total	50	

From the above table, of the 6 social networking services used by students, Whatsapp is seen to be mostly used by student with 60%, Facebook 6%, Twitter 8%, Youtube 6%, Intsgram 10%. Following Chart for further displays the graphical distribution of the number of users.

Table 6 Purpose of using Social Network Services

S. No	Purpose	No. of Answers	Percentage
1	To Updating Myself	20	40
2	To Entertaining	27	54
3	To Learn more Information	30	60
4	To Keep in touch with Families and Friends	21	42
5	To make Professional	4	8
6	To Develop Friends Circle	15	30
7	To Share Videos, Pictures etc.,	13	26
8	To Time Passing	18	36

In this table shows that Students were asked to choose more than one option. 40% students use social network services to updating themselves, 54% students use social network services to entertaining, 60% students use social network services to find information, 8% to make business contact, 42% to keep in touch with family & friends, 30% for developing friends circle, 26% to share videos /picture etc, and 36% for time passing. Following chart displays the graphical distribution of the percentages above.

Table 7 Effects of Social Networking Services on Academic Performance

S. No	Effects of Social Networking Services	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Positive	28	56
2	Negative	14	28
3	No Affect	8	16
	Total	50	

56% students think that Social Networking Services has a positive effect on academics. 28% students think that Social Networking Services has a negative effect on academics and 16% students think that Social Networking Services do not effect on their academic work. Following chart displays the graphical distribution of the Effects of Social Networking Services on Academic Performance.

Findings

- Most of the students are members in less than 2 social network services.
- 42% were using it since more than 2 years.
- Out of 6 social networking services used by students, Whatsapp is seen to be mostly used by student.
- 60% students use social network services for the purpose to find information
- 56% students think that Social Networking Services has a positive effect on academics.

Conclusion

It is concluded that, in recent years; use of social network services has become very popular all around the world due to a great development of technology. The basic purpose behind conducting this study was to know the effect of student who spend most of the time in Social network services. The findings from conducted studies has find out to be mostly positive because students spend time of their day activities on these social network services have able to share and generate new ideas and concepts related to their academic performance. The students need to create stability between the use of Social Network Services for their growth of academic performance.

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